

Big Questions in Classrooms – Epistemic Insight Theory of Change

Situation

Students in English primary and secondary schools (and to a lesser extent other home nations [UK]) experience school learning in a compartmentalised fashion. There are limited opportunities for teachers within the current assessment focuses delivery and/or for students in their own learning to make meaningful connections between the nature and creation of knowledge in one academic discipline and another. This is particularly compounded in relation to the science and religion classrooms where curriculum emphasis, perceptions of social and cultural sensitivities and teacher confidence mean that these boundaries are particularly “impermeable”.

Aims

To improve teacher confidence in addressing topics that bridge the science and religion classrooms, particularly in relations to Big Questions at the interface of science/technology and society. To equip teachers with pedagogical approaches and tools that facilitated interdisciplinary learning in relation to the distinctiveness and interaction of disciplines in addressing Big Questions. Increase students’ epistemic insight (knowledge about knowledge) so that they express greater intellectual humility and reduced uncritical scientism empowering them to see science and religion as not necessarily incompatible.

Process

Impact

Inputs

Activities

Outputs

Short Term Outcomes

Intermediate Outcomes

Long Term Outcomes

Schools

- Staff involvement in training and co-creation of learning interventions
- Commitment to dedicated curriculum time; and/or consistent/ shared approaches to EI language/tools; and/or regular interdisciplinary sessions/homework opportunities.
- Delivery of learning opportunities
- Delivery of data collection tools
- **LASAR**
- Development of interventions + learning materials
- Provision of pedagogical tools and support
- Provision of whole school and departmental training
- Quality assurance of co-created activities.
- Analysis and evaluation of interventions

- Teachers received training prior to session delivery
- Students receive a sustained intervention of (at least fortnightly) a series of sessions that equip them with learning tools and opportunities to apply tools to addressing real word opportunities/problems.

- Series of fully resourced lessons and assessments that address a range of interdisciplinary combinations.
- Student EI toolkit that is transferrable to wider learning.
- Teacher EI toolkit and planning tools to support (continued) development of whole school EI ethos.

- Increase in attitude towards learning.
- Increase confidence in addressing interdisciplinary Big Questions.
- Improved academic resilience in using multiple disciplines to improve their responses (expressed intellectual humility)
- Improved academic attainment in being able to contextualise and apply learning
- Increased epistemic insight and reflection on skills and techniques learnt throughout project and ability to apply these in new contexts/to new challenges

- Increase # of students entering EBacc
- Increase in academic attainment at KS4
- Increase in students’ academic self confidence
- Increased opportunities for teachers to collaborate cross-departmentally
- Increase in interdisciplinary activities in school (homework, discrete curriculum programmes, collapsed timetable days etc.)
- Increased interest in delivery and assessment of students’ epistemic insight and expressed intellectual humility.

- Increased Attainment 8 Score [student achieved in 8 core subjects] at individual level student and school level
- Increased Progress 8 Score [extend to which student’s have exceeded predicted grades] at individual level student and school level
- Change in external assessments to value students’ interdisciplinary responses to extended evaluation and analysis questions

Rationale & Assumptions

Rationale: An increase in students’ understanding of the nature of and interaction between knowledge formation across their curriculum subject enables them to be more confidence and independent learners with greater resilience to misinformation. This increase in academic self-concept and epistemic insight enables students to be rational and compassionate thinkers able to address complex social and technological issues concerning society today.

Assumptions: Relationships with schools are strong and translate into good buy-in; schools sign updated data agreements and provide timely access to required data; students receive the full programme; improved reading confidence, academic resilience, epistemic insight, and attitude towards learning translates into improved attainment; production of resources in time for delivery.